

Milana Ranković, LL.M.,*
Teaching Assistant, PhD student,
Faculty of Law University of Montenegro,
Republic of Montenegro

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PUBLIC POLICY EXCEPTION UNDER THE 2019 HCCH JUDGMENTS CONVENTION

Abstract: *This paper provides an analysis of the refusal of recognition and enforcement of foreign judgments on public policy grounds within the framework of the Hague Judgments Convention. Paper examines general public policy exception clause, which is provided in Art. 7(1)(c) of Convention and specific exceptions, that may in some situations, if conditions are fulfilled, also constitute public policy, which are provided in Art. 7(1)(a), (b), (e) and (f), 7(2), and 10 of the Convention. Further, given that the European Union is contracting party to the Convention, paper assesses how the public policy exception has been applied in the law of the European Union and analyses relationship between two regimes. Paper specifically observes whether and to what extent two regimes are complementary and potential issues that could arise in its practical application. Aim is to examine whether diversity between approaches on regional and international level can ultimately lead to discrepancies in practice, which could restrict the reciprocal enforcement of judgments and do they have the potential to undermine the desired uniformity established by the Convention.*

Keywords: "Public Policy Exception", "Recognition and Enforcement", "HCCH", "2019 Judgements Convention".

1. Introduction

Judgments Convention is a significant development of contemporary private international law, which has great importance for international cooperation in civil and commercial matters, because it establishes minimum international standards for the global circulation of judgements. It is a „game-

* milanatmc@gmail.com

changer¹ that promises to revolutionize free movement of judgements by ensuring that judgments made in one country signatory are recognized and enforced in another.

Convention is based on three-pillars: scope, eligibility and refusal,² which make it an instrument that is capable to harmonize legal standards for recognition and enforcement, streamlining the process and by preventing any review of the merits of the foreign judgments³, leading us in a new era of global judicial cooperation.

This paper focuses on the public policy as ground for refusal of recognition and enforcement of foreign judgments in the Judgments Convention. Convention provides a general public policy exception clause in Art. 7(1)(c), as well as specific exceptions in Art. 7(1)(a), (b), (e) and (f), 7(2), and 10 of Convention. Paper further examines the public policy exception in law of the European Union, given that European Union is contracting party to the Convention.

The core values that constitute European public policy include those fundamental principles established in primary European Union law and in the European Convention on Human Rights. Paper analyses how public policy exception has been interpreted in the case law of CJEU and ECHR. Finally, the relationship between two regimes is examined, are they complementary and potential issues of interpretation that could emerge in their practical application. Consideration is also given to possible approaches for addressing some of the issues that may arise. How this Convention might navigate the balance between the expectation of uniformity, the flexible nature of the public policy exception, the trend towards specifying applications of this exception in international conventions, and the maintained sovereignty of States.

2. Public Policy Exception in Judgements Convention

Because of the modest and flexible nature of the Judgments Convention, in some aspects, it lacks self-sufficiency. Namely, for the foreign judgement to be recognized under Convention regime, the requested State shall confirm that judgment is eligible for recognition, by establishing that the jurisdictional requirements (filters) set out in Article 6 (for judgements on rights in

¹ Judgments Convention is often described as game-changer by Secretary General of HCCH, Mr. Christophe Bernasconi.

² Cardoso C.J, *Implementing the Hague Judgments Convention*, New York University Law Review, 97 (5), 2022, p. 1519.

³ Art. 4, para. 2, of the Convention on the Recognition and Enforcement of Foreign Judgments in Civil or Commercial Matters, 2 July 2019 (in further text: „Judgements Convention“).

rem in immovable property) and Article 5 for all judgements, are fulfilled. If a judgment was made by court that had jurisdiction according to one of the filters, the contracting States to the Judgments Convention are under the obligation to allow the recognition and enforcement of that judgment, safe for a number of exceptions i.e., exhaustive grounds for refusal listed in Art. 7, when the requesting court may refuse to recognize judgement.⁴

Convention adopts term „may“ similarly as its model New York Convention. Therefore, it is suggested that it should be interpreted similarly, i.e. that it provides discretion to each Contracting State to choose from discretionary refusal, mandatory refusal, refusal with limited discretion or any combination of the three. Degree of discretion will depend on judge of the country where enforcement is sought, because it is related to constitutional issue of delimiting judicial power.⁵

Also, burden of proof is left to the country of enforcement, who is to decide either the burden of proof is on a party resisting recognition or to provide for an *ex officio* review. This is the case because it is closely related to other procedural matters, and Convention leaves the procedure for recognition and enforcement to the legal framework of the requested State. Convention does not prevent recognition under national law.⁶

Traditionally, public policy exception is provided as a ground for refusal of recognition in Art. 7 (1) (c) of Convention. It can be considered as an inherent limit for the obligation of uniform interpretation, which protects domestic legal order by preventing foreign decisions that are incompatible with the fundamental principles of domestic law from having effects in particular state. It therefore defines the outer limits of tolerance of national law and represents a “safe zone” from the application of foreign law and recognition of foreign judgments which are manifestly contrary with domestic public policy.

Convention strives to strike a balance between two conflicting interests. Namely, a decision of a foreign court is an act of a foreign State and its recognition in another state can only be allowed if it is in accordance with the basic principles of justice. For these reasons, every country wants to protect its legal order from foreign decisions that are unacceptable for it, by requiring high threshold of “manifest incompatibility” with the requested

⁴ Poesen, M., Is specific jurisdiction dead and did we murder it? An appraisal of the Brussels Ia Regulation in the globalizing context of the HCCH 2019 Judgments Convention, *Uniform Law Review*, 26 (1), 2021, p. 10.

⁵ Jang, J., The Public Policy Exception Under the New 2019 HCCH Judgments Convention, *Netherlands International Law Review*, 2020, p. 102.

⁶ Art. 15 of the Judgements Convention.

State's public policy. On the other hand, the reasons of international cooperation and the freedom of movement of people, goods, services and capital dictate that states minimize barriers that would limit or unnecessarily complicate movement of judgements. States are not isolated, they are connected with common interests and values, and they strive to coordinate with each other within international or regional organizations. Some states may adopt a common public policy, such as the public policy established by European Union for its member states.⁷

2.1. General exception clause

General Public Policy Exception Clause contained in Art. 7(1)(c) provides that recognition and enforcement may be refused if it would be manifestly incompatible with the public policy of the requested State, including situations where the specific proceedings leading to the judgment were incompatible with fundamental principles of procedural fairness of that State and situations involving infringements of security or sovereignty of that State.

This broad exception covers three different subsections: manifestly incompatible with the public policy of the requested State, incompatible with fundamental principles of procedural fairness and infringements of security or sovereignty.

2.1.1. Important features

Some important features of public policy exception under Convention regime may be distinguished from the wording of Art. 7 (1) (c).

First, relevant is public policy of the state where enforcement is sought. Second, the public policy should qualify as international public policy.⁸ Sometimes it may be difficult to ascertain what constitutes international public policy because "few subjects are more vague, more difficult to seize and more controversial than that of the existence, contents and function of a public policy which would be 'really' or 'truly' international."⁹ International public policy is a subset of national public policy, distinguished by a specific source of obligation rooted in international law, that the concerned state must uphold. Purely international public policy exists if obligation that arises under fun-

⁷ Jang, J, *op.cit.* p. 98.

⁸ *Ibid.*, p. 100.

⁹ Lalive, P. *Transnational (or Truly International) Public Policy and International Arbitration*, Comparative Arbitration Practice and Public Policy in Arbitration, Kluwer Law International 1987, (Sanders, P., ed.), p. 259.

damental rule of international law would be infringed, if such judgment was recognized or enforced.¹⁰

Third, there should be a link between case and requested state and that connection exists if request for enforcement is sought. Fourth is the request that recognizing foreign judgement would cause harmful consequence to the fundamental legal principles of the State where enforcement is sought. In order for the public policy exception to be applied, it is necessary that the effects of violation of procedural principles are incompatible with the state of recognition, it is not enough that the rules of procedure of the state of decision and the state of recognition differ.¹¹

Fifth, from the wording of the Art. 7 (1) (c) it is clear that Convention adopts division into substantive and procedural public policy. Sixth, the foreign judgement may be refused recognition only if the effects of this judgement are contrary to domestic public policy. Seventh, court of the country where recognition is sought shall examine if conditions are met and there shall be no review on merits, meaning that there shall be no re-examination of facts and laws. Namely, to recognize a decision means to give a foreign court decision the effect of a *res iudicata* that it has in the country where the decision was made.¹² The adjudicated matter is considered to be finally resolved and the same matter cannot be reinitiated.

On the other hand, in order to decide if substantive public policy would be violated by recognizing or enforcing a foreign judgment, court of the country where recognition is sought must look into the merits.¹³ However, this substantive investigation is limited by the fact that public policy intervenes only to confirm and end a public policy violation limit. The public policy clause is an exception and as such must be interpreted narrowly and strictly, it requires that the limits of its application be determined. Finally, if a separate part of judgement cannot be recognized due to violation of public policy or for other reasons, the remaining part of the judgment may be.

To sum up, effects of foreign judgement shall be “manifestly incompatible with the public policy of the requested State“, which is a high threshold,

¹⁰ Hoško, T., Public Policy as an exception to free movement within the internal market and the European judicial area: A Comparison, CYELP 10, 2014, p. 198.

¹¹ Kostić-Mandić, M., *Priznanje i izvršenje stranih sudskih odluka u novom međunarodnom privatnom pravu Crne Gore*, Zbornik radova Udruženja pravnika Crne Gore, 2015, p. 10.

¹² Bogdan, M., *Concise Introduction to EU Private International Law: Third Edition*, Europa Law Publishing; 3rd edition, 2016, p. 71.

¹³ Stanivuković, M., Živković, M., *Međunarodno privatno pravo opšti deo*, Službeni glasnik, 2023, p. 461.

intended to ensure that judgments are recognised and enforced by other States signatories, unless there is a compelling public policy reason not to do so in a particular case. This high threshold is similar in other international instruments, so case law under the New York Convention¹⁴ may be utilized to provide guidance to courts on situations where the breach is substantial enough to trigger the application of Art. 7(1)(c).

2.1.2. *Infringements of security or sovereignty*

State Security and sovereignty is broad description of what may, in some situations, be considered as public policy, provided that the general features for the application of public policy exception are fulfilled in particular case.¹⁵

Purpose of including explicit reference to state security and sovereignty in Art. 7(1)(c) was to prevent narrow interpretation, that might exclude these interests, because they may not always qualify as the fundamental policy of the State where enforcement is sought.¹⁶

Also, 1965 Service Convention explicitly mentioned state sovereignty and security, so there were concerns that if it wasn't included in the wording of Convention, it could lead to a *contrario* interpretation.¹⁷

This provision should be read in conjunction with all other provisions regarding State actions and immunities in the Convention. The States that demanded that all of these clauses are included also intended to guarantee that they could use their sovereignty as a component of their public policy at the level of recognition and enforcement.¹⁸

It should be mentioned that there are views in doctrine stating that in some situations concept of transnational public policy can sublimate state sovereignty. Also, courts of some countries (for example, Australian Courts and Supreme Court of India) have rejected to apply transnational public policy, based on the pre-eminence of state sovereignty and by contending that

¹⁴ The Convention on the Recognition and Enforcement of Foreign Arbitral Awards, 10 June 1958 (New York Convention).

¹⁵ Jang, J, *op. cit.* p. 104.

¹⁶ Trakman, L., *Aligning State Sovereignty with Transnational Public Policy*, Tulane Law Review, 93 (2) 2018, p. 207-268.

¹⁷ Jang, J, *op. cit.* p. 104.

¹⁸ Kessedjian, C., *Comment on the Hague Convention of 2 July 2019 on the Recognition and Enforcement of Foreign Judgments in Civil or Commercial Matters Is the Hague Convention of 2 July 2019 a useful tool for companies who are conducting international activities?*, NIPR, 2020, p., 32.

“international” concept of public policy is “unworkable” and have applied narrow concept adopted in the enforcement state.¹⁹

The examples of infringements of state security and sovereignty that may constitute public policy is refusing to recognize foreign decisions in order to safeguard the forum’s national security, preserving public health and the environment from the importation of dangerous goods, enforcing state sanctions imposed on trade with foreign nations,²⁰ or violation of a UN sanction in the one Member State, which, if simply international public policy is not applied, may result in enforcement in another Member State.²¹

2.1.3. Procedural unfairness

According to Art.7(1)(c) procedural unfairness is considered as a sub-category of the public policy. This means that a judgment must be “manifestly incompatible” with the public policy of the state where recognition is sought and that the specific proceedings leading to the judgment shall be incompatible with fundamental principles of procedural fairness.²² For instance, that would be the case when the right to a fair trial is guaranteed by the constitution, making it unconstitutional to acknowledge a foreign judgment obtained through proceedings that violated these fundamental principles.

There is an overlap with specific defences which can also be invoked for certain aspects of procedural public policy. This includes Art. 7(1)(a) concerning notice, Art.7(1)(b) addressing fraud, and Art. 7(1)(e) and (f) pertaining to conflicts of judgments. Additionally, Art. 7(2) focuses on parallel proceedings, while Art. 10 deals with non-compensatory damages.

There were some concerns raised in doctrine that treating procedural unfairness as a sub-set of public policy can dilute other procedural protections guaranteed by Convention.²³ However, that would not be the case because this overlapping is designed to ensure that parties undergoing recognition and enforcement proceedings receive sufficient procedural safeguards, regardless of the specific manner in which these issues are dealt with in the requested State.

¹⁹ Trakman, L., *op.cit.* 231. For instance, this approach has been taken by Supreme Court of India.

²⁰ *Ibid.*, p. 223.

²¹ Beaumont, P., Johnston, E., *Can Exequatur Be Abolished In Brussels Whilst Retaining a Public Policy Defence?*, 6, 2010, JPIL, p.259.

²² Born, G., *The Hague Convention on Choice of Court Agreements: A Critical Assessment*, University of Pennsylvania Law Review 169 (8) 2021, para. 2122.

²³ *Ibid.* This Concern was raised in relation to Choice of Court Convention, but same issue may arise under Judgements Convention.

2.2. Specific exceptions

Convention provides specific exceptions in Art. 7(1)(a), (b), (e) and (f), 7(2), and 10, which may also constitute public policy if conditions are met.

2.2.1. Parallel Proceedings

The Convention deals with the issue of parallel proceedings in Art.7(1) (e) and (f) and Art.7(2).

The issue of inconsistent judgements may arise in situations when more than one court has jurisdiction over a dispute and parallel or multiple proceedings are being brought in front of these courts, which may result in multiple judgements.²⁴

Art.7 (1)(e) provides that recognition may be refused if the judgment is inconsistent with a judgment given by a court of the requested State in a dispute between the same parties; The judgement of the requested court does not need to be given prior to competing judgement and it does not have to be based on the same subject matter.²⁵ Art.7 (1) (f) deals with cases when both conflicting judgements are from foreign States and provides that recognition may be refused if the judgment is inconsistent with an earlier judgment given by a court of another State between the same parties on the same subject matter, provided that the earlier judgment fulfils the conditions necessary for its recognition in the requested State. Art. 7 (2) addresses situations where proceedings are still pending in the requested State when recognition or enforcement of a judgment given in another State is sought. This is because *lis pendens* in another State cannot be invoked as a ground for refusal. Recognition and enforcement may be refused if following three conditions are cumulatively met: the proceedings pending in the requested State shall be between the same parties on the same subject matter; the court of the requested State was seized before the court of origin and there is a close connection between the dispute and the requested State.

2.2.2. Non-Compensatory damages

Public policy is also resorted to in cases when the nature of damages awarded is unacceptable, because they are significantly different from the type of damages provided for in domestic law²⁶ or for that form of relation-

²⁴ Garcimartín, F., Saumier, G., *Explanatory Report on the Convention of 2 July 2019 on the Recognition and Enforcement of Foreign Judgments in Civil or Commercial Matters*, Hague Conference on Private International Law, 2020, p. 122.

²⁵ *Ibid.*, p. 123.

²⁶ Kostić, M., *Međunarodno privatno pravo*, Pravni fakultet Podgorica, 2017, p. 105.

ship such sanctions cannot be considered in civil law. For instance, damages in civil law are fundamentally different from the system of punitive damages, which has primary purpose punishment and general prevention, and where, punishing offenders and suppressing similar behaviour is left to criminal and administrative sanctions.²⁷

Therefore, Art. 10 (1) of Convention contains public policy provision relating specifically to the punitive damages, which provides that “recognition or enforcement of a judgment may be refused if, and to the extent that, the judgment awards damages, including exemplary or punitive damages, that do not compensate a party for actual loss or harm suffered” and provides the territorial distribution of powers to impose them. Each Contracting State has the freedom to recognize and enforce non-compensatory damages according to its national law.

It should be also noted that the court of the country where recognition is sought, is not bound by characterization of the damages as compensatory or non-compensatory, from the court of the origin, although it may serve as a point of reference.²⁸ So, in some situations it may be difficult to establish the difference between compensatory and non-compensatory damages, i.e. should the damage be characterized in accordance with the law of the country where enforcement is sought or there should be autonomous interpretation.

According to the Explanatory Report, refusal of enforcement on the basis of public policy could operate only when it is obvious from the judgment that the award appears to go beyond the actual loss or harm suffered.²⁹ In that respect, in addition to punitive damages, “in exceptional cases, damages which are characterised as compensatory by the court of origin could also fall under this provision”. According to legal writings, under Convention, refusal of enforcement of a foreign judgment is therefore allowed in so far

²⁷ It is incompatible with the fundamental principles and with the basic goals of the system of compensation for damages, to make a decision that in the relationship between the parties in one tort, the injured party can in addition to compensatory, the injured party can receive punitive damages, that have as goal punishment and general prevention. For these reasons, the enforcement of the part of the foreign judgment ordering the company that filed the complaint to pay punitive damages, in addition to compensatory damages and costs, cannot be allowed, because it is contrary to the public policy. Case: *Northon I, Oregon Partnership v. Mansei Kogyo Co*, Judgement of the Supreme Court of Japan, 1997, Stanivuković, M., *Praktikum za međunarodno privatno pravo*, Pravni fakultet, Centar za izdavačku delatnost, Novi Sad, 2004, p.245.

²⁸ Jang, J, *op. cit.* p. 110.

²⁹ *Ibid.*, p. 109.

as it concerns punitive damages or damages that are otherwise excessive.³⁰ The Explanatory Report states that autonomous interpretation should be applied, because it is the most appropriate for the International Convention.

Whether the punitive nature of damages is a pre-condition for accepting a possible violation of public policy, was one of the questions addressed in the recent CJEU preliminary ruling in *Real Madrid Club de Fútbol, vEE, Société Éditrice du Monde SA*.³¹ The court held that in absolutely exceptional cases, recourse may be to the public policy clause, even where the decision imposing a penalty relates to compensatory damages³² and solely in connection with other arguments concerning fundamental rights that constitute public policy in the Member State in which enforcement is sought.³³

³⁰ Garcimartín, F., Saumier, G, *op.cit.* p.132.

³¹ The following outlines the pertinent facts of the case. The newspaper Le Monde published an article by journalist E.E., alleging that football clubs Real Madrid and FC Barcelona had hired Dr. X. Fuentes, who was known for running a doping ring in the cycling world. The article's extract, featured on the front page, included a drawing captioned «Doping: first cycling, now football», showing a cyclist in Spanish colors surrounded by football players and syringes. This story was widely shared, especially by Spanish media. Le Monde published a denial letter from Real Madrid but did not comment further. Subsequently, Real Madrid and a member of its medical team filed a lawsuit for damages in front of a Spanish court. The lawsuit resulted in an order from the Spanish court that the defendants in the main proceedings pay EUR 300,000 to Real Madrid and EUR 30,000 to the member of its medical team. The court also ordered that its decision be published in the newspaper Le Monde. Recognition and enforcement of this judgment were sought in France. The Paris Court of Appeal held that recognition or enforcement of the judgments imposing those penalties was at variance to an unacceptable degree with French international public policy by interfering with freedom of expression. In its preliminary ruling, the CJEU held that the court must refuse or revoke a declaration of enforceability of that judgment where enforcement of that judgment would give rise to a manifest breach of the freedom of expression guaranteed in Article 11 of the Charter. Such a breach exists where enforcement of the judgment gives rise to a potential deterrent effect, which exists if the overall sum the payment is manifestly unreasonable, having regard to the nature and the economic situation of the person concerned. For instance, that sum is several dozen times the standard minimum salary in the Member State in which enforcement is sought, or it would represent a manifest threat to the financial stability. The court of the Member State in which enforcement is sought may take account of the seriousness of the wrong and the extent of the harm only in determining whether, even though the overall sum of a penalty is a priori manifestly unreasonable, it is appropriate for counteracting the effects of defamatory statements.

³² Case C - 633/22, *Real Madrid Club de Fútbol, AEvEE, Société Éditrice du Monde SA*[ECLI:EU:C:2024:127] para. 149.

³³ In reaching its decision Court followed the reasoning from the Case C-302/13, *flyLAL-Lithuanian Airlines*[EU:C:2014:2319] para. 56-58.

3. Public Policy Exception in Brussels Regime

The free movement of judgments is often referred as the fifth freedom of EU, which, together with the four basic freedoms³⁴ ensures operation of Internal market.

Brussels Regime³⁵ operates within a limited number of relatively similar European countries, linked by both an integration project and common judicial and legislative organs (i.e., the Court of Justice of EU and the EU Parliament, Council and Commission).

If recognition and enforcement of judgement made in one EU country is sought in another member state, the Brussels Regime applies. Judgment made in one member state is automatically considered recognized in another, without any procedure.³⁶ The judgement should be in “civil and commercial matter” and the party seeking recognition should provide copy of judgement by which its authenticity can be established and certificate issued on a standard form by the court of origin.³⁷ Therefore, no formalities such as legalization are required. However, court may request an official (certified) translation of the decision. The rules are the same regardless of whether the party requesting the recognition and enforcement procedure has nationality or residence within a member state.³⁸ Interested party may request a separate declaratory decision, that would establish once for all purposes, that there are no grounds for refusing recognition³⁹.

Decision of a court of the Member state recognizing judgement from non-member state cannot be subject to Brussels Regime.⁴⁰

On the recognition and enforcement of judgements made in third countries that are not EU members, Judgements Convention applies, if that third country is also a party to Convention. If a non-member state is not a party to Judgement Convention, national rules apply.⁴¹ Therefore, this is the area

³⁴ Hoško, T., *op.cit.* p. 212.

³⁵ Brussels Regime consists of Brussels Convention, Brussels Regulation and the Brussels I Regulation (recast).

³⁶ Art. 36, para 1, of the Regulation (EU) No 1215/2012 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 December 2012 on jurisdiction and the recognition and enforcement of judgments in civil and commercial matters (Recast) (in further text: „Brussels I Regulation (recast)“).

³⁷ Art. 37 of the Brussels I Regulation (recast).

³⁸ Bogdan, M., *op. cit.* p.72

³⁹ Art. 36, para. 2 of the Brussels I Regulation (recast).

⁴⁰ Bogdan, M., *op. cit.* 71. C-129/92, *OwensBank v Bracco* [1994] ECRI-00117.

⁴¹ Kostić, M., *op.cit.* p.201.

where importance of Judgements Convention is highlighted, because if third country is signatory of Judgements Convention, EU member states have the obligation to recognize judgement,⁴² safe for the exception explicitly provided in Convention.

Grounds for refusal of recognition are set exhaustively in Art. 45 of Convention,⁴³ and public policy, as most general reason for refusal, is provided in that article. This means that EU Member States have not yet achieved complete alignment in core principles, essential values and human rights protections to fully eliminate the public policy exception. Member States may avail themselves of the negative function of the public policy to prevent the unwanted effects of a foreign judgment by avoiding its application or recognition and enforcement.⁴⁴

Term “European public policy” refers to public policy of the European Union and Council of Europe, established in first line by the European Convention on Human Rights. It is somewhat difficult to precisely define what constitutes EU public policy, but in principle we can say that Primary Sources of EU Law, and undoubtedly, the four basic freedoms of movement of persons, goods, capital and services, which aim to ensure a common market, are part of the fundamental principles of the EU, as well as many other fundamental values. EU law is a component of national laws of its member states.⁴⁵ It follows that freedom of Member States to define their public policy is limited.⁴⁶

The *Krombach* is a landmark case where CJEU provided some guidance to Member States on the application of public policy exception. Namely, three cumulative conditions must be met: a significant discrepancy between the rule applied in the state of origin and a rule in the state of recognition, a resulting violation of a fundamental principle in the state of recognition and enforcement due to this divergence, and that this violation of a fundamental

⁴² Art. 4, para. 1. of the Judgements Convention.

⁴³ The refusal is mandatory, as set out in Case C-80/00, *Italian Leather SpA v WECO Polstermöbel GmbH & Co* [2000] ECR I-04995.

⁴⁴ Hoško, T., *op. cit.*, p. 195.

⁴⁵ Case C-126/97, *Eco Swiss China Time Ltd v Benetton International NV* [1999] ECR I 03055.

⁴⁶ In the EU, there were even proposals to abolish the possibility of invoking the public policy exception clause between member states, for the reason that human rights guaranteed by the ECHR provide sufficient protection. Nevertheless, it turned out that even in the countries of Europe who share the same legal tradition and have same basic values, exceptions are possible. It is recognized that some countries have specific values that must be respected, despite the fact that they represent a restriction on the freedom of movement of judgments. Beaumont, P., Johnston, E., *Can exequatur be abolished in Brussels (I) whilst retaining a public policy defence?*, *Journal of Private International Law*, 6 (2) 2010, p. 277.

principle constitutes a “manifest breach of a rule of law regarded as essential in the legal order of the State in which enforcement is sought”.⁴⁷

According to this formula, it is not for the CJEU to define the content of the public policy of a Member State, it is nonetheless required to review the limits within which the courts of a Member State in which enforcement is sought may have recourse to the concept of public policy.⁴⁸ Judges are not free to refuse recognition at their own discretion, in relation to the individual concept of public policy in enforcing state, because of the strict interpretation of public policy exception by CJEU. They “close their doors” only when the application of foreign law violates some fundamental principle of justice, morality, some deep-rooted value.⁴⁹ Also, it should be noted that CJEU can change the limits within which the courts of the member states may resort to their legal order and can find that excessive use is against the regulation.⁵⁰

The criteria for applying the public policy exception, as established by the case-law of the CJEU, can be summarized as follows:

First is that recognition of such judgement would result in the *manifest breach* of a rule of law regarded as essential in the legal order of the State in which enforcement is sought or of a right recognised as being fundamental within that legal order. Public policy exception cannot be invoked solely on the ground that there is a discrepancy between the applicable laws and from reviewing the accuracy of the findings of law or fact made by the court of the Member State of origin, due to the prohibition on the review on substance.

Second, public policy exception shall not be applied to jurisdiction, because it would undermine the mutual trust between the member states.⁵¹ Judgement made in member state shall be recognized even if due to Art. 6 it was given on national jurisdiction ground deemed exorbitant in Member state where recognition is sought.⁵² Third, use of public-policy is precluded if party invoked some other more specific objection from Art.45.

Fourth, the institute of public policy must be interpreted strictly “because it represents an obstacle to free movement of judgements and a

⁴⁷ Case C-7/98, *Dieter Krombach v André Bamberski* [2000] ECR I-01935.

⁴⁸ *Ibid.*, para. 23.

⁴⁹ Chong, A., *The public policy and mandatory rules of third countries in international contracts*, *Journal of Private International Law*, 2 (1) 2006, p. 29.

⁵⁰ Bogdan, M., p. 73.

⁵¹ Art. 45, para. 3. of the Brussels I Regulation (recast).

⁵² Bariatti, S., *Cases and Materials on EU private international law*, Hart publishing, Oxford and Portland, Oregon, 2011, p.165.

simplified recognition and enforcement mechanism, as one of the basic goals of the convention.” Recourse to the public policy clause should only be made in *exceptional cases*. The idea behind the Brussels Regime is based on mutual trust... Member states have given up the right to apply the provisions of their internal laws in order to simplify the procedure of recognition and enforcement in the EU.⁵³

This classic formula should be supplemented by two elements which further restrict the interpretation of the concept of public policy within EU.⁵⁴

The first element relates to fundamental rights. The Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union and the European Convention on Human Rights provide a complementary framework for safeguarding the fundamental values of the EU and its Member States in civil and commercial contexts. This complementarity fosters mutual trust between Member States, particularly in situations where EU law may not be applicable. Human rights are the most important part of the institute of public policy, and if the recognition of foreign decisions was possible without this exception, it would give primacy to the freedom of movement of judgments over fundamental rights. As stated by ECHR in *Loizidou* case⁵⁵ European Convention on Human Rights is a “constitutional instrument of the European public policy (*ordre public*).”⁵⁶

In this context, it should be noted that there are scholarly views that the refusal to enforce judgment may amount to an interference with the applicant’s right to a fair hearing Art. 6 (1) of the ECHR.⁵⁷

The second element is mutual trust. This suggests that rejecting or not enforcing a judgment from a Member State undermines the mutual trust in

⁵³ Beaumont, P., Johnston, E, *op. cit.*, p. 251.

⁵⁴ Case C - 633/22, *Real Madrid Club de Fútbol, AEvEE, Société Éditrice du Monde SA* [ECLI:EU:C:2024:127] para. 47.

⁵⁵ *Loizidou v. Turkey*, Application no. 15318/89, Judgement from 18 December 1996.

⁵⁶ Kramberger Šker, J., *European public policy (with an emphasis on exequatur proceedings)*, Journal of Private International Law 7 (3), 2011, p. 463.

⁵⁷ There is an open question whether the right to a fair hearing and to effective legal protection, embodied in Article 6(1) of the ECHR, actually requires that the foreign judgment is enforced. The European Court of Human Rights has until now, so far as is apparent, recognised such a right only in relation to enforcement in the State where the judgment was made. Whether Article 6(1) of the ECHR also makes the recognition and enforcement of foreign judgments obligatory can remain an open question here, since the Brussels I Regulation confers a corresponding right in any case. In any event, Article 6(1) of the ECHR would not lead to any result other than an appropriate application of the regulation consistent with respect for human rights. C-420/07, *Apostolides* [EU:C:2008:749], para. 52; See also: Kinsch, P., *Enforcement as a Fundamental Right*, *Nederlands Internationaal Privaatrecht*, No 4, 2014, p. 543.

judicial administration among EU Member States, which is fundamental for functioning of Brussels Regime. This trust stems not just from legislative decisions by EU institutions but is rooted in primary law.

4. Relationship between regimes

Relationship between Brussels Regime and Judgements Convention is an evolving and multi-faceted one.⁵⁸ However, primacy of EU Instruments is provided in Art.23 (4) which states that Convention “shall not affect” the application of rules of Regional Economic Organization that is party to Convention, if the rules were adopted before conclusion of Convention or after Convention was concluded, to the extent that they do not affect obligations under Art. 6 towards Contracting states that are not members of EU.⁵⁹

That means that, after the Convention is concluded, EU cannot adopt a rule, allowing for the circulation among its Member States of judgments on a right *in rem* over immovable property situated in another Contracting State.⁶⁰

This point is confirmed in case law of CJEU, who found, in *Kadi* case that it has the authority to assess whether EU law, which incorporates international law, aligns with other EU legislation, thereby adopting a distinctly dualist approach in its perspective on the international legal framework.⁶¹

5. Potential issues in interpretation

Judgements Convention requires mandatory recognition of judgements made in all countries signatories, which makes it reasonable to question to what extent public policy exception can protect country where recognition or enforcement is sought, from foreign judgements that are incompatible

⁵⁸ In the context of relationships between regimes it should be also stated that there are views, expressed by Prof. Hartley, that the Brussels Regulation, rather than the New York Convention, served as the model for the Hague Convention. Hartley, T. *Is the 2005 Hague Choice-of-Court Convention Really a Threat to Justice and Fair Play? A Reply to Gary Born*, [Electronic version], 2021, Retrieved July 2024 from <https://eapil.org/2021/06/30/is-the-2005-hague-choice-of-court-convention-really-a-threat-to-justice-and-fair-play-a-reply-to-gary-born/>.

⁵⁹ Sender, P. M., *The 2019 Hague Judgments Convention: its conclusion and the road ahead. In Asian Academy of International Law, Sinergy and Security: the Keys to Sustainable Global Investment: Proceedings of the 2019 Colloquium on International Law* (Ed.), Asian Academy of International Law Limited, p. 8.

⁶⁰ Garcimartín, F., Saumier, G, *op.cit.*, p. 167.

⁶¹ Joined cases C-402 & 415/05P, *Kadi & Al Barakaat Int'l Found v Council & Comm'n* [2008] ECR I-6351, paras. 287-290.

with its fundamental values, specially having in mind that countries worldwide can have different standards in the rule of law.

The question arises when will the violation of fundamental principles be manifest enough to allow reliance on the public policy exception, and would it be sufficient to protect legal order of the country of enforcement from serious denials of justice. For instance, refusing recognition on public policy grounds in situations that might involve corruption or bribery is extremely difficult in recognition procedure, because there could be difficulties in obtaining evidence, language, cost, risks of official interference etc.

There is a lack of predictability and legal certainty in the operation of public policy exception. Hence, it remains to be seen how public policy exception, “notion to fit all intentions and applications”,⁶² due to its variability in space and time, will operate in practice of the courts of the countries signatories⁶³, who have different legal traditions and standards, and no single body that would resolve issues of interpretation that may arise in practice.

Harmonization of approaches can be very difficult task on global level⁶⁴, because there are fundamental discrepancies in perception of fundamental values and required level of procedural safeguards, which might undermine the desired uniformity established by the Convention.

A solution to some issues may be found in fact that Contracting parties may consider the practical operation of specific HCCH instruments at the regular convening of Special Commission. The Special Commission can issue authoritative recommendations and advice on uniform interpretation of the Convention and its support can be significant in interpretation of public policy exception in the context of Judgements Convention.

6. Conclusion

Public Policy Exception is widely accepted as a ground for the refusal of the recognition and enforcement of foreign judgments in national legislations and in international legal instruments. Paper analyzed Public Policy Exception under 2019 Hague Judgments Convention, followed by its analysis under Brussels Regime. The paper examines the relationship between the

⁶² Hoško, T., *op. cit.*, p. 211.

⁶³ At the moment of writing this paper, Judgements Convention is signed by the United States, North Macedonia, Israel, Costa Rica, Russia, Montenegro and, most recently, the United Kingdom, and it entered into force between the EU Member States (excluding Denmark), Ukraine and Uruguay.

⁶⁴ Trakman, L., *op. cit.*, p. 224.

two regimes, specifically investigating their complementarity and the interpretative challenges that may arise in practical implementation, with the aim to question if the diversity between approaches on regional and international level could potentially undermine desired uniformity intended by the Convention.

Summary

Public Policy Exception is generally accepted as a ground for the refusal of the recognition and enforcement of foreign judgments in national legislations and in international legal instruments. Even though it has some common characteristics, its content is diverse and depends on the law of requested State. Namely, each state has its own set of fundamental values that constitute public policy and they naturally differ. However, some states may adopt a common public policy, such as the public policy established by European Union for its member states.

In this paper, we firstly analyze regime for refusal of recognition and enforcement of foreign judgments on public policy grounds in the Hague Judgments Convention. Convention provides a general reservation clause in Article 7(1)(c), as well as specific reservations in Articles 7(1)(a), (b), (e) and (f), 7(2), and 10 of Convention. In some cases, specific reservations may also be considered as procedural public policy, if conditions are fulfilled. Therefore, we examine whether this overlap can cause interpretation problems in practice, especially having in mind that Article 13 of Convention leaves the procedure to law of the requested State.

Then, given that the European Union is contracting party to the Convention, we examine the public policy exception in law of the European Union. On EU level, public policy has mostly negative function and there were attempts to restrict its application only to exceptional cases. The core values that constitute European public policy include those fundamental principles established in primary European Union law and in the European Convention on Human Rights. We proceed to analyze how public policy has been interpreted in the case law of CJEU and ECHR.

Analysis finally considers the relationship between two regimes. Specifically, it examines whether they are complementary and potential issues of interpretation that could emerge in its practical application. Consideration is also given to possible approaches for addressing and resolving any issues that may arise.

Aim is to examine whether diversity between approaches can ultimately lead to profound policy discrepancies, which could restrict the reciprocal enforcement of judgments, and do they have the potential to undermine the desired uniformity established by the Convention.

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